

Understanding Confessionalism: Psychological Insights in the Poetry of Kamala Das and Sylvia Plath

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ABSTRACT

Kamala Das and Sylvia Plath are distinguished poets of confessional poetry. Confessional poetry is a branch of post-modern poetry. It has heralded a new era of English poetry. In confessional poetry poets bare their hearts to have psychic reliefs. Plath is an American confessional poet and Kamala Das is a traditional Indian woman writing poetry to exude her intense repressive feeling of sexual exploitation and humiliation in her conjugal life as well as in her society. Both the poets have written poems to articulate their strong mortified emotions. They have defied taboos and showed their courage to voice their protest and resentment against the patriarchal society. They have used poetry as a medium of their oppressed voice and the victims of the sexist society. Their poetry is an analysis and exploration of their tormented minds.

Keywords: Confessional poetry, Psyche, Self-expression, Self-analysis, Oppressed voice, Individual liberty, Feminism

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I. INTRODUCTION

Confessionalism might be specified as a distinct form or branch of post-modernism. As a new genre of post-modern English poetry it is predominantly a psychological analysis of the poet's private experiences and personal feelings, mainly traumatic. Emily Dickinson was the harbinger of confessional poetry in English literature. Confessional poetry betrays the repressed heart and mind of the poet. It discloses personal revelations and secrets, often written in the first person. It, like autobiography and memoir, has come to occupy a distinct place in English literature as 'confessional literature'. In this form of poetry the poet gives expression to exclusively personal, intimate, sometimes shocking details of or about himself or herself. Confessional poetry originated in the United States of America during the late 1950s and the early 1960s. Sylvia Plath, Anne Sexton, N. D. Snodgrass, Theodore Roethake or John Berryman became popular as confessional poets in America. The subject matter on which they shed light was once considered taboo. The poetry with the confessional theme produced in between 1950 and 1960 treated such subject as previously not been openly discussed in American poetry. Kamala Das distinguished herself as a confessional poet and is equated with Sylvia Plath.

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